

Wor, The Biak Traditional Folksongs: Their Types And Symbols

Reimundus Raymond Fatubun, Markus Ricky Rumansara

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 15, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Wor, Biak, Folksong, Type, Function</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5784732</p>	<p><i>The Biak tribe inhabits the Biak Island, in the Cenderawasih Bay, to the north of the island Papua. For generations this tribe has preserved their art traditions, one of which is called wor. Wor is a kind of folksong accompanied by traditional musical instrument called tandip and dances. Wor is divided into several types, distinguished by melody, rhythm, and social functions. Every wor is divided into a kadwor or tip and a fuar or root. Wor is an obligatory ritual that must be performed by the Biak people throughout life. To save this tradition from extinction, this study was done. This study tried to find out the types and functions of wor. The study found ten types: (1)Kankarem, (2) Byeuser, (3) Erisam, (4) Kayoub, (5) Mamun, (6)Wonggei, (7) Arbur, (8) Kansyaru, (9)Randan, and (10)Morinkin. These are the important symbols found in the wor lyrics: 1) the Morning Star, Sampari; (2) the bird of Paradise; (3) the sireb (wooden drum); (4)ayumbab, (a place for comfort and happiness); (5) kamasan(the black smith); (6) manwen (witch); (7) sares (antiques); (8) benambojareno(merriment); (9) 'yen Saoneko' (the sand of Saoneko); and (10) apenobesasyek(burned stones and the smell of food).</i></p>

Introduction

As is true with modern people, one way of how traditional people would communicate their concerns about aspects of life would be through folksongs. Just like any other traditional folks throughout the world, the Biak people also have traditional folksongs collectively called *wor*. In some lyrics of the traditional folksongs, people reveal their life complexity like pleasures, pain, worries, love, wisdom, etc. through the lyrics.

These song lyrics record the life realities mentioned above for the people themselves to inspect. The song lyrics may remind them about the favorable realities to be maintained and nourished while the unfavorable ones need to be avoided and prevented from happening again. The writers of folksongs are usually unknown. Every single song has messages about the life realities to keep telling the people. Exactly, what life realities are there brought up by these folksongs to continue reminding people about these realities?

Biak is an example of the tribes that is blessed with a lot of cultural heritage of which one of them is the *wor*, the traditional folksongs. With the world becoming smaller because of information technology there is a possibility that these traditional folksongs may be slowly disappearing. The original traditional rhythm and wisdom contained in the songs may be lost.

A number of Biak cultural heritage have been studied including folktales but studies on these folksongs have not been properly done. This study is an effort to save these folksongs.

One study done on the *wor* folksongs was by Simon and Yampolsky (1998) entitled *Music of Biak, Irian Jaya: Wor, Church Songs, Yospan*. This was actually a Smithsonian recording project. This study was about music of the *wor* because they recorded the *wor* folksongs and discusses them using musical terminology. They also discuss some development the *wor* folksongs entering into what is now called *Yospan* which is actually a modern folkdance resulting from combining a number of dance movements, particularly the foot movements from various tribes in Papua, including the Biak ethnic group.

Since studies on the *wor* folksongs are still limited, a number of studies on folksongs from other cultures are presented below instead.

Similar to the discussion of the development of the Biak *wor*, Maliangkay (2002) brought up the revival of the South Korean folksongs presenting a sample folksong called "Tondollari". The Koreans are taking this art seriously in order to make a living out of it. They are trying to give their interpretation to the folksong and they have been successful. It would be proper of the Biak folksongs to go through similar path.

Another kind of folksong is the Japanese the 'holeholebushi' (Sasaki, 2014)

which are actually folksongs with Japanese characteristics like their traditional poems Haiku and Tanka but with themes emerging from the Japanese immigrants working on plantations with other immigrants from other places in Hawai'i back there between 1880s and 1940s. The themes included their work, living conditions, love, lust, despair, and courage in their new environments on the Hawai'i plantations. Just like the Black American blues, for example, these Japanese folksongs record their history back to the past many of which reflect perspectives from Japanese women. This is the first serious work on this genre.

Kotsonis' work (2014) in some way similar to Simon and Yampolsky's (1998) in that she looks at the folksongs from a more musical point of view, from a conductor's understanding of choral arrangements of ten Appalachian folksongs in their cultural contexts than just studying the lyrics. The key elements she analyzed were meter, tempo, melody, text, accompaniment, dialect and ornamentation. This is an attempt to bring folksongs to a higher status just like what the Koreans did as discussed above.

Apart from containing themes like pain, happiness, love, kindness etc., some folksongs may contain some other information such as information on ethnobotany just like the study done by Herrero and Cardaño (2015). They studied 7,012 traditional Spanish folksongs to identify various species of plants with various categories mentioned in the songs. For example, they found that from the families mentioned, the highest number of citations were: Rosaceae, Poaceae, Vitaceae, and Caryophyllaceae. Or, in 50.7% of cases, alluded to beauty of which the most frequently symbols were the rose and the carnation.

If Simon and Yampolsky (1998) touched on the development of the Biak *wor*, Maliangkay (2002) on efforts for the revival of the South Korean folksongs, and Herrero and Cardaño (2015) on ethnobotany, Inyang (2018) focused his study on the folksongs and the potential significance on sustainability of the ecosystem. Through folksongs performances, the information about ecosystem contained in the songs may be used to educate the populace about the development communication and environmental awareness. He even goes on to recommend the integration of traditional folksongs and local ecological knowledge in environmental awareness and development communication programs incorporated into the reading materials in the schools, creative education syllabus, and contemporary media programs content.

None of the works reviewed above talked about types and symbols in folksongs. The Japanese one, the 'holeholebushi', in a way is similar because one of the issues that was brought up in the discussion was themes; the Spanish one talked about plants mentioned in the folksongs but the songs were studied more from botanical point of view.

This present study is very significant because it tries to look at the *wor* folksongs from their types and symbols. Apart from knowing both their types according to their cultural functions, this study also examines any significant symbols found in the lyrics since important cultural symbols and concepts may be present in literature and arts alike. Through this present study, it is hoped that, like the Koreans who tried to elevate the status of their folksongs, the Biak people would start to think about how to bring this genre to a more modern adaptation to make a living out of it.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Folk Song

Folksongs are unique artifacts distinguished by their display of a relatively personalized, lyrical, form of communication. Cuddon (1998, p.323) states that "This kind of song belongs to oral tradition ... and is thus passed on from mouth to mouth. It is a communal form of expression and appears to be universal." Baldick, (2001, p. 99) mentions that folk song is a song of unknown authorship that has passed on, preserved, and adapted in an oral tradition before later being written or recorded.

2.1.1 Functions of Folk Songs

The main purpose of literary works is to entertain and educate its audience (Barry, 1995, p. 22). Since folksong lyrics may be treated as poems and surely, they are poems that are sung, they may contain many things to offer. Like other literary works, folk song lyrics may become what the Indonesians call 'tuntunan dan tontonan' (cf. 'docere et delectare'), teaching and delighting at the same time. Wilkinson (2019) conveys several reasons why the folk song is important in life because they spark memories, connect the generations, help everyone to feel competent, and is a quickest way to engage.

2.1.2 What is *Wor*?

A folk song usually has simple, short, with repetitive lyrics (except some ballads), not particularly artfully high-level, created by ordinary folk(s) and represents shared emotions about life. This can be seen in most folk songs. Usually, these songs reflect on shared cultural heritage, happiness, and pain/sadness, or certain social problems, anxiety about this life, belief in higher power, acts of heroism, kindness, love saying, beauty, sadness, separation, customs, etc. Usually, the melody is simple and natural because the emotion of the song comes from the people's own environment. Folk song is an art that ordinary people can participate as members of society in it. *Wor* is certainly shares these characteristics.

Rumansara (2003, p. 214) defines *wor* as an activity closely tied to obligatory traditional ceremonies, *munara*. *Wor* can also be also a number of songs sung by the people in traditional ceremonies passed down from one generation to the next orally. In this situation people sing and dance at the same time.

In many civilizations, one can observe that there is coherence between dance, music, and belief and this is seen in these *wor* folk songs. Folk songs can also be created based on mythology, history, legend, some even revolve around the epic level like the Biak Manarmakeri myth. Because this *wor* is still very conserved, it is hoped that it will survive for a long period of time into the future and can even be modified to bring different styles.

Rutherford and Yampolsky maintain that “*Wor* is a deeply rooted in every corner of Biak people life.... The central medium for expressing their social identity, *Wor* served to legitimate clan claims to territory, to express demands for gift of food and drink, to evoke sympathy, support, anger, or sorrow.” (1996, p. 5)

Rumansara (2003, p. 216) mentions that *wor* was a means by which the people used to worship their supreme deity called *Manseren Nanggi* aka *Manseren Manggundi*. Messengers of this deity are called *Konor* and *Mon* (Mansoben, 2003, p. 25). Throughout their life, the Biak people are required to carry out these *wor*, particularly the *munara*, (Rumansara, 2003, p. 214), according to their functions in life and throughout their lifetime.

2.2 Symbolism

In the past people thought in images, particularly in metaphors. Even today there are still tribes who talk in images using metaphors in tribal meetings when they get together to discuss tribal matters. Saunier (in Circlot, 1971, p. xxx) states that symbols are:

“the synthesizing expression of a marvellous science, now forgotten by men, ... they show us all that has been and will be, in one immutable form ... their didactic function as timeless objects *per se*, at least in their intimate structure, for the other factors are cultural or personal variants.”

The symbols contained some certain meanings that is concealed that has to be revealed. Lurker (in Biedermann, 1994, p. ix) maintains that “The meaning of the symbols does not lie in the symbol itself but point to something else outside it.” Symbols used by traditional societies are difficult to grasp particularly when they are inherited from older generations in their various types of arts like folkstories, folksongs, sayings, etc because according to Tresidder (2011, p. 6) “Traditional symbols form a language which become more mysterious as we move further away from the thought patterns and worldview of those who produced it.”

In analysing symbols, Circlot (1971, p. xxxvi) states that there are a number of basic ideas and suppositions that allow us to do so. He goes on to remind us to bear in mind that: “(a) Nothing is meaningless or neutral: everything is significant. (b) Nothing is independent, everything is some way related to something else. (c) The quantitative becomes the qualitative in certain essentials which, in fact, precisely constitute the meaning of the quantity. (d) Everything is serial. (e) Series are related one to another as to position, and the components of each series are related as to meaning.

2.3 Previous Studies

There is a number of studies related to issues under discussion. Sriyono, *et al* (2015) discusses *The Cultural Codes in Oral Literature of Biak Papua*, a study aiming to describe the cultural codes in the Biak oral literature, using Umberto Eco’s semiotic approach.

Dimara’s study *Bentuk dan Implementasi Nilai Pendidikan Karakter Dalam Cerita Mitos Manarmakeri Suku Biak Numfor Provinsi Papua* aims to reveal the educational value in the *Manarmakeri* myth among the Biak tribe and a description of their life and social reality and as a medium to foster intelligence, love, and respect as part of the ancestral heritage.

Usmany’s *Biak Noemfoor Shipping Before the 19th Century the Review of Maritime History* discusses the history of Biak traditional knowledge in making sail, expedition during 16th century, explanations on topography, and how it influences people’s natural ability, especially in astronomy.

Rumbekwan’s study *Peristiwa-Peristiwa Perang Suku Tradisional di Pesisir Utara Papua* is a study about the historiography reconstruction of life dynamic of tribes in the North of Papua Island. The time was around 15th century to 19th. There are some moments recorded in this study, one of which is the civil war among tribes in Papua, and the Biak people was the dominant one during that era. This study also presents the hegemony of Biak people in dominating the territory from Cenderawasih Bay to north of Papuan coast.

In a research report entitled *Biak Numfor Oral Prose*, Fatubun (2017) found various types of folktales among the Biak tribe community. He also wrote (2017) “An Archetypal Reading the *Manarmakeri* Myth from Biak, Papua: Its Development Implications and Political Significance” discussing the big myth in Biak i.e. *Manarmakeri* in its development implications and political significance in the thinking and behavior of the Biak people in everyday life. In his *Archetypes in Biak Folktales: Characters, Symbols, and Concepts*, Fatubun (2021, p. 244), when discussing these issues, states that

“Politically, the most important archetypal characters ... are ‘the pure virgin maiden’, ‘the hero’, ‘the outcast’, ‘the virgin birth’, Environmentally the most important archetypal characters are ‘wise old man’, Madira with the 7 protectors. Politically the most important archetypal symbol is ‘the Morning Star’, ..., and the archetypal concepts are ‘Paradise’, ‘Supreme God’, ..., and ‘the Era of Bountiful’

3. RESEARCH METHOD

A qualitative inquiry is, according to Ary, *et al* (2014, p. 421) a generic term for a variety of ... research approaches variously labeled as ethnography, naturalistic inquiry, case studies, fieldwork, and observation. Since this is a study of an aspect of an ethnic group, this is an ethnographic study, carried out from February 2021 through the end of March, 2021.

The research site was the Biak-Numfor regency, where most indigenous people of Biak live and most importantly the elderly having knowledge of history, cultural background, beliefs, arts, and especially about *Wor* because they served as valid sources of information. Data were obtained from field study, interviews, and recordings, as well as data from social media and books. For validity enhancement triangulation, cross-validation (Sugiono, 2007, p. 372) in this study was fulfilled through sources, theories, researchers, and methods (Alwasilah, 2008).

In the analysis of the symbols, the Peircean model of Semiotics was used (Deladalle, 2000, p. 14). It is said that this model is a somewhat different from Saussurean one in that:

“In contrast to Saussure’s model of the sign in the form of a ‘self-contained dyad’, Peirce offered a triadic (three-part) model consisting of: 1. The representamen: the form which the sign takes (not necessarily material, though usually interpreted as such) – called by some theorists the ‘sign vehicle’. 2. An interpretant: not an interpreter but rather the sense made of the sign. 3. An object: something beyond the sign to which it refers (a referent).” (Chandler, 2007, p. 29)

A sign is context bound. A sign may mean one thing for one context but another thing for another context. Take the sign x, for example. It may mean ‘danger’ in traffic rules, but ‘multiply’ in math. The Peircean semiotic triangle looks like the following:

Peircean semiotic triangle

(From <https://www.bing.com/images/search?q=peircean+semiotic+triangle&id>)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 *Kadwor* (Tip) and *Fuar* (Root) of *Wor*

Wor is divided into a number of types differentiated by melody, rhythm, and or social function. The lyrics are divided into *kadwor* or tip and *fuar* or root and commonly sung accompanied by a traditional musical instrument called *Sandip* (Rutherford and Yampolsky, 1996, pp. 5-6). An example of *kadwor* and *fuar* are the following:

Kadwor	Fuar
1. Imyundisorwamanjasa, rwamanjas 2. Suworomindimamukeseppenboimuyunsukon dandi ra bebuka-iboisukonsurower	1. Aryo naeko Suan Bebayaemyundisorwamanjasa, rwamanjasa 2. Suworomindimamukeseppenboimuyun dandi ra bebuka-iboinsoso bin ansuiwasukonsurower
Tip	Root
1. It is a good thing you came, a good thing you came 2. So that they can sing you a wor to record to take abroad and open for them to listen to	1. Oh Mr. Big, it is a good thing you came, a good thing you came 2. So that the young men can sing you a wor to record to take abroad and open for those young ladies over there to listen to

4.2 Types of *Wor* and Their Symbols

There are many types of *wor* for various purposes and functions. Apart from the ten general types discussed here, there many other ones celebrated by the tribe in the past such as *worKoreri*, *wor fan nanggi*, *worRumsram*, *wormararen*, *worsom*, *worm mon*, etc. (Kamma, 1981). The *worKoreri* was very rarely celebrated because of its complexity and probably because of its sacredness.

In general, there are ten types of *wor* found in this study: (1) *Kankarem*, (2) *Byeuser/Beyuser*, (3) *Erisam*, (4) *Kayoub*, (5) *Mamun*, (6) *Wonggei*, (7) *Arbur*, (8) *Kansyaru*, (9) *Randan*, and (10) *Morinkin*(Fatubun and Rumansara, 2021). This present article deals with the analysis of each type in terms of function and symbols found in the *wor* lyrics.

1. *Kankarem*

Kankarem, an opener *wor*, is sung in a reciprocal manner in a ceremony. This type of *wor* is always displayed in the form of reciprocity. Usually, it is used as the opening *wor* in a particular traditional ceremony. The style and lyrics in this folk song are believed to be able to encourage the spirit of everyone involved in the folk party.

Nowadays, this *woris* collaborated with singing and dancing to become welcome dances to community leaders considered to play important roles for a community, e.g. government officials, church leaders, etc.

One very important symbol in this *wor* is the Morning Star, *Sampari*, also known as *Makmeser* or *Kumeser*. Stars, like other symbols, have various meanings. Stars in the American flag indicates the number of states, but the stars in the Singaporean flag stand for democracy, peace, progress, law, and equality (Biedermann, 1994, p.325). This *Sampari* is related to the most sacred myth among the Biak people, the *Manarmakeri* myth. Since the Biak people are among the most developing tribes in Papua, ideas and ideals from this tribe may influence the Papuans in general. In fact, politically this Morning Star symbol has been used in the Free Papua Movement because of its significance in the myth.

Very specifically, this Star has been one of the most important symbols discussed by Fatubun in his “An Archetypal Reading of the *Manarmakeri* Myth from Biak, Papua: Its Development Implications and Political Significance (2021, p. 240; see also Fatubun et al 2002; Fatubun, 2017, p. 161), he explains that:

“...*Sampari* can also mediate the miracle given to *Manarmakeri*, and the knowledge of an era of bountiful called ‘*Koreri*’ the Morning Star is the most prominent symbol in this story and now it has very political significance.... This object symbolizes freedom, independence, and the like. ‘*Sampari*’, the Morning Star which has been known for quite a long time now in Papua, especially in the flag of the Free Papua Movement, actually comes from this symbol. The star in the flag is actually ‘*Sampari*’, the Morning Star in this Biak myth.”

The *Kankarem* *wor* lyrics and its English version is given below.

The Biak Language	English
<i>Wowo wo makiwadekikyankondo</i>	O star there ascend to the throne
<i>Mendepkarmandorekdorekarwo</i>	Beside the cloud, bird singing, chirping,
<i>Samparimakiwadekikyankondo</i>	Morning star there ascends to the throne
<i>Mandepkarmandorekdorekarwo</i>	Beside the cloud, bird chirping, morning

2. *Byeuser*

This type of *wor* is actually narrative, the best example being the sacred *byeuserKoreri* telling the story of the most important tribal myth the *Manarmakeri* as explained in the *Kankarem* above. The *ByeuserKoreri* consists of 42 stanzas written in unrhymed triplets. The first two stanzas are the introduction, followed by stanza 3 up to stanza 10 as the main song which is the monologue of *Manarmakeri*, then comes an intermezzo from stanza 11 through stanza 15. The main song resumes from stanza 16 to stanza 42 (Kamma, 1972, pp. 59-63). This is the main song sung in the *ByeuserKoreri* with one person impersonating *Manarmakeri*.

In the contemporary use, a *byeuser* is sung to tell the experience of an individual or somebody else’s by a person or a group of people to tell stories or events experienced by the person, the group, or others. *Byeuser* may also be sung to express one’s feelings or expression of gratitude to the ruler of the universe *ManserenNanggi* for his blessings and protection throughout the life of both individuals and relatives in a group because of doing good deeds to others. In addition, *byeuser* may also be used as a medium of request from a man to his sister for her apology.

The important symbol in this *wor* is the bird and understood here as the bird of paradise, *Cenderawasih*. This bird is so beautiful that various tribes have their own myth about this amazing bird. One such myth is “Wowoi, The First Bird of Paradise” translated by Fatubun (2016). The tale goes like this: A foster mother wanted to marry her own foster son, but the son thought it was immoral to do so. The boy prayed to the Almighty to find a way out. He put his arrows at the back of both sides of his shoulders and lo and behold. The arrows transformed

to become his wings and he flew away. The bird in this context is a symbol of morality that a son cannot marry his own mother, never mind a foster mother.

The *byeuseris* the following with its English translation.

The Biak Language	English
<i>Aye man yeja man berow</i>	Oh my bird, bird that flies
<i>Befnakberarwai sup marinyejano</i>	Play, visit my land of paradise
<i>Rasinewaburiwawaikaruribeyao</i>	Today you go, turn away from me
<i>Aroroiroro</i>	What a pity
<i>Aye manyeja man berow</i>	Oh my bird, the bird that flies
<i>Befnakro Papua sup marinyejano</i>	Play in Papua, my land of paradise

3. *Erisam*

In the past this was both a battle and a victory song which was a fighting song to encourage and praise to lead people to battle and eventually to victory. *Erisam*, particularly sung to entertain a leader on his way to battle and to lift up his bravery. 'Er' means 'house', especially a small house on a boat; 'isam' means 'hot'. So, the word 'erisam' can be interpreted as a 'hot house', referring to the person in the house. This *wor* is used to entertain him in the hut. This was done because it was believed that every verse in the lyrics of this folk song was able to evoke courage and a sense of spirit in the soul of the leader to defeat the enemy. In general it was sung in the past as a long voyages song to make people strong to endure the sea hardship. It was also a part of the *worKoreri* sung at night recounting the journey of Manseren Manggundi which was Manarmakeri himself.

Today, this *woris* used as a part of performances in celebrating important religious events, governmental events, etc. It is believed that each lyric can liven up the atmosphere and make the party more memorable.

In this *wor* there is the mention of the musical instrument the *sireb*, made of several important and expensive items believed to be very long-lasting, but in fact as is true with anything in this world, the *sireb* will decay and perish although it is the most important and cherished musical instrument in the Biak traditional performances. This *sireb* symbolism indicates that both the *sireb* itself and as a representation of the Biak art, *wor*, should be maintained and kept well to endure the test of time. It has to be passed on to the next generations otherwise it would soon disappear into oblivion.

The *erisamis* given below with its English translation.

The Biak Language	English
<i>Woo.. o ryokiraisaibo-isaibo</i>	Wow, the sound is echoing
<i>Isai murabaroberosinansyabepono</i>	Keep on echoing, from ancestors long gone
<i>Woo aryonaeko</i>	O brother
<i>Sireb ai maremiryokiraisaibo-isaibo</i>	The sound of the wooden drum of *maremi echoing
<i>Isai murabaroberosinansyabepono</i>	Go on echoing, from ancestors long gone

4. *Kayoub*

This type of *wor* was originally a part of the *worKoreri*. It was sung before dawn to describe the struggle between *Sampari*, the Morning Star and Manarmakeri in the sacred myth of *Manarmakeri* which alludes to the struggle between Jacob and the angel in the Bible (Gen. 32:22-32). The wrestle was won by Manarmakeri forcing *Sampari* to bless him with the knowledge of the *Koreri* through the birth of his son Manabew (Fatubun, 2017, p. 161). This song was a lamentation here. Every clan lamented their dead during a period of 4 through 8 nights. The specific *kayoub* for this *worKoreri* is *kayoubKummesri*, the *kayoub* of the Morning Star, sung towards daybreak. Actually *kayoub* is any song sung to celebrate the ancestors, their great deeds, possessions, songs, voyages, victories, etc. (Kamma, 1971, pp. 99-100).

Kayoub, as performed today is meant to comfort sorrowful people or those who mourn their dead ones or to soothe children whose mothers have left them temporarily or for good. Since it is a more personal *wor* and not performed publicly, it is not very often found.

The symbol found in this *wor* is the word *ayumbab* which describes a place where people can have comfort and happiness. Since Biak is an island, it refers more to the beautiful beaches with comforting breezes. However, it can also refer to forests with cooling shady trees. In short it indicates comfort for both body and soul.

The example of *Kayoub* is given with its English rendering below:

The Biak Language	English
<i>Aye kyansidowunirawakakyuki</i>	Oh, when he cries, you take, coax him
<i>Ro babirawaayumbabbabirawa</i>	Down there, a cool place down there
<i>Aryoawinekapirakysidowunirawakakyuki</i>	Oh madam, when the baby cries, take, coax him
<i>Ro babirawaayumbabbabirawa</i>	Down there, a cool place down there

5. Mamun

Mamun is another type of *wor*, sung to describe the situations before and after a battle; this type of *wor* was used to describe the state of war in the past. *Mamun* was actually *awor* sung all the way through a voyage (Kamma, 1981, p.291) to uplift the spirit. In the pre-war situation, this *wor* functioned as a form of ritual to ask for protection and victory from *ManserenNanggi*, ruler of the universe. In the post-war period the ancestors of Biak people usually told the state of war using this *wor*, either telling the victory or remembering war events in the past. Because it was believed that magical power is in every lyric, the lyrics can awaken the fighting spirit or courage of anyone involved in war. If the war was lost, then they still had to respect people lost in the battlefield through singing this folk song.

This *wor* is still alive and found in the life of the Biak community in the present era because the values and motifs of the struggle found in each lyric can be applied in human struggle in life. This *wor* is also used along with other types of *wor* to enliven folk parties in modern times, such as welcoming important guests.

The word *kamasan* is the symbol in focus here. *Kamasan* is one of the archetypal characters that is 'protector of the smith' found in Biak folktales as discussed by Fatubun in 2021 (p. 238). The god *KamasanMangkarwaidi*, son of Madira, was protector of the smith and therefore he was "... entrusted this responsibility ... in the tale 'Negeri Sasori' by his father Madira. *Kamasan*'s duty was to make sure wise use of weapon, not used to scare or destroy other countries." Nowadays, *kamasan* is the symbol of a wise learned person who has both knowledge to share with others and wisdom for others to follow.

The following is the *mamun* with its English rendering.

Biak Language	English
<i>Siponyama, siponyama</i>	They come, they come
<i>Siponyama, siponyama</i>	They come, they come
<i>Siponyama, manggamumbeyarokamasan</i>	Here they come, steel spies, black smith
<i>Sup kobebero way rareni</i>	Our land on the prow of the boat
<i>Siponyama, siponyama</i>	They come, they come

6. Wonggei

Wonggei is another kind of *wor*, sung to tell good news, invite people to a thanksgiving, invite others to engage in worship for the Almighty for He has blessed people with good things in life.

In the past, after the performance of this *wor*, a shaman (*mon*) would carry out a ritual to communicate with *ManserenNanggi* to get clues about the blessings given to people later in their efforts to make a living. In the *Manarmakeri* myth, Biak people know and believe in a second life in another world, the 'Koreri' paradise where *ManserenNanggi* enthroned.

In modern times, with the advent of Christianity, this *wor* is carried out in the form of praise and worship to Lord Jesus for eternal life in heaven replacing the old myth. Until now *wonggei* can still be found even though there is a shift, from local belief to the Christian faith. The *wonggei* given here is a Christian one, filled with Biblical teaching.

The symbol to be discussed in this *wor* is the word related to witchcraft, 'manwen.'

Woiyo..Naekosraryenamgonene
 Mgoramakobeoserimakorowerparensarefoineno, refoineno
 Imboikunimakobukifyarkenembobedineno
 Kombroro-Kombroro, Kombrordo, wosora kafkofen kobenaneno
 Kombroro-Kombroro-Kombrordo wosoaryawin manwen naneno
 Nanema woso refo ine imewer
 Nayano-naryano-woso refo ine ryama ma fyarkorko
 Koswaryayeko ma Kobe osero

O my brothers

You come, we come together to hear the message of this Bible, this Bible

But we take it as our guide in life

We repent, we repent, we repent from scoffing

We repent, we repent, we repent of witchcraft

The Bible dislikes all of these

These things, these things the Bible says, came to teach us

We love each other and are united

This word 'manwen' is found many times in the folktales from the Biak tribe. Fatubun (2021, p. 234) when discussing the archetypal characters, one of the archetypal characters is the devil figure. 'Manwen' is one of the devil figures found, for example, in the tale *ManwenAbir*, in which the 'manwen' tried to kill the inhabitants by hiding among taro plants ('abir', Biak language); in the tale *KyumInsanai*, there is a group of 'manwen' who caught a small boy. Luckily this child could free himself; in the tale *Anak Yang Tidak Mendengar Nasihat Orang Tua*, another small boy was kidnapped by a group of 'manwen', but he could escape; and in the tale *ManwenInggouni*, the 'manwen' wanted to annihilate the village dwellers, another boy was asked to observe the arrival of these 'manwen', and he was caught but was able to escape.

Although the evil power is not as strongly believed as it used to be in the past, this word has come to be associated with witches or any other evil doers and the like.

7. *Arbur*

Some people from the Biak tribe and others from other parts of the world may still believe in earthly supernatural spirits. In the Biak tradition, one such belief is manifested in the 'arbur' which is spirit of level six in the Biak spirit world which is believed to inhabit trees (Fatubun, 2021, p. 231). Indeed 'Arbur' is a word in Biak language referring to spirits inhabiting large trees. *Arbur*, as a *wor*, can be interpreted as prayers of worship aimed at keeping the evil spirits, the 'arbur', out of human life. This folk song was used during traditional feasts introducing a baby into the world, after three days of his or her birth.

Unlike *Wonggei*, the magical values in *Arbur* are considered contrary to Christian belief and are now forbidden, and therefore, no longer implemented, although still maintained, and displayed with other styles and motifs as the example given here.

The symbol to be discussed here is the *sares*. These are the antiques like plates, bowls, etc. Since these *sares* were from outside for example, from China, they were very highly valued because they were not produced locally. To welcome somebody important and new to Biak, a *sares* plate would be placed on the ground for the person to put a foot on it. This indicates the respect of the people to the person.

The *arbur* is below with its English version.

Biak Language	English
<i>Wekiwareforodorie</i>	You go up, you stand inside
<i>WekiwareforodoriesaresByakine</i>	You go up, you stand inside, this Biak sares

8. *Kansyaru*

Kansyaru is a *wor* usually sung to raise the spirit of other people so that they would want to be involved in an event being performed. This is done to ensure people that working together with many other people would make a difficult job easy to handle and ensure its success. In other words, this *wor* is carried out to invite people to participate in an event. Since it is a public *wor*, it is still found in Biak communities up to the present time. The lyrics have even been taken and combined with a number of other types to create newer social gathering songs like *Yospan* (short for *YosimPancar*). This *Yospan* is now the most popular songs and music accompanied with dances just like a *wor* and is very often competed all over Papua during national festivities like Indonesia's Independence Day celebrations.

The word *benambojareno* is a symbol since it symbolizes togetherness in joy and happiness because of being together in a *wor* beating the tifa drum, singing, and dancing together with many other people, usually relatives or even a clan. Being in a *benambojareno* situation would tie and unite the people being involved in it.

Below is the *workansyaru* with its English version.

Biak Language	English
<i>Kwon bapeworeso</i>	You don't sit but you stand up
<i>Wakimamobekinsirebyabobenambojareno</i>	You see the one holding the tifa, happy
<i>Aryonaek-sraro kwon bapeworeso</i>	O brothers and sisters, do not sit, stand up
<i>Wakimamobekinsireb</i>	You see, the one holding the tifa drum of maremi wood, rejoicing
<i>maremiyabobenambojareno</i>	

9. *Randan*

This is another type of *wor*. This Biak folk song issuing to ask for protection and blessings upon a person or a group of people. Usually, this *wor* is shown in traditional parties such as 'kapanaknik', haircuts, performed to a first child, while those carrying out the hair cutting ceremony are the brothers of the child's mother. This practice of hair cutting still prevails in the life of the Biak communities to this day, but the ritual undergoes a significant shift. The traditional *Randan* is no longer used as a medium of blessing and protection from supernatural spirits, but replaced by Christian teachings with local symbolism still intact.

If we look at the symbolism, since Biak is an island with many other smaller islands surrounding it, we can see that coastal and marine symbolisms are quite dominant in their arts including the song lyrics here. The phrase 'yen Saoneko' means 'the sand of Saoneko.' Since most sandy beaches are white, they symbolize purity and cleanliness, so from the context, the Biak people believe that the Saoneko sandy beach is the most proper and sacred place where the people could ask for the supreme deity to come down to listen to their prayers and to bless them.

Below is the *worrandan* with its English version.

Biak Language	English
<i>Neno, nenonedadoikyondo</i>	Lord, Lord He came down to sit on
<i>Yen Saoneko-yen Saoneko</i>	Saoneko sand, Saoneko sand
<i>Yore mamo, mamo dadoikyondo</i>	I you see, you see Him down sitting on
<i>Yen Saoneko, yen Saoneko</i>	Saoneko sand, Saoneko sand
<i>Neno, neno nene Manseren Bebai Dado</i>	Lord, Lord Most holy Great He came down to sit on
<i>Kyondo</i>	Saoneko sand, Saoneko sand
<i>Yen Saoneko, Yen Saoneko</i>	

10. *Morinkin*

It is another type of *wor*, containing magical words. The function of this song is to ask for protection from the ruler spirit of nature for family members who carry out a traditional feast. In other words, *Morinkin* is sung to ask the Almighty to protect those holding the ceremony.

The phrase *apenobesasyek* although indicates the burned stones and the smell of the food from an earthen oven of Papuan style permeating the air, it actually has a higher and more philosophical meaning. The real meaning of this phrase here is the process of maturing a person's life and driving all bad luck from the person's life in the days to come.

Below is the *wormorinkin* with its English version.

Biak Language	English
<i>Kamayowya, Nakamayowe...</i>	Cover, wrap, cover, wrap up
<i>Apenobesasyekworokapanaknik</i>	Embers of hair cutting events
<i>Kamayowe.... ya, nakamayowe</i>	Close, wrap, close, wrap up

5. CONCLUSION

From the ten types of *wor*, one can see that these folk songs are sung for various functions: to encourage the spirit of everyone in a folk party or to welcome community leaders; to tell the experience of an individual or somebody else's or to express gratitude to *ManserenNanggi*, or to ask for an apology; to entertain a leader on his way to a battlefield and to lift up his bravery, or for celebrating religious, governmental events, and other similar occasions; to comfort those who are sad; to describe the situations before and after a battle; to tell good news, invite people to a thanksgiving, invite others to engage in worship for the almighty; to drive evil spirits away; to inspire someone to participate in an activity; and to ask for blessings upon someone.

The important symbols found in the *wor* lyrics are: 1) *Sampari*, the Morning Star, also known as *Makmeser* or *Kumeser* symbolizing freedom from suffering, and death; (2) the bird of Paradise symbolizing morality; (3) the *sireb* (wooden drum) symbolising the Biak art and its maintenance to be passed on to the next generations; (4) *ayumbab*, symbolising a place where people can have comfort and happiness; (5) *kamasan* (the black smith) symbolising a wise learned person who has both knowledge and wisdom; (6) *manwen* (witch) symbolising the devil figure very often trying to destroy the inhabitants; (7) *sares* (antiques) symbolising respect; (8) *benambojareno* (merriment) symbolizing togetherness in joy and happiness; (9) 'yen Saoneko' (the sand of Saoneko) symbolizing spiritual purity and cleanliness; and (10) *apenobesasyek* (burned stones and the smell of food) indicating the process of maturing a person's life and driving all bad luck away.

REFERENCES

- Alwasilah, C. (2008). *Pokoknya Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Pustaka Jaya.
- Andrew B, A. N. (2004). *Literature, Criticism and Theory*. London: Longman Pearson.
- Ary, Donald; Jacobs, Lucy Cheser; Sorensen, Chris; and Walker, David. (2014). *Introduction to Research in Education*. Belmont: Wadsworth.
- Baldick, C. (2001). *The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Literary Terms*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Biedermann, Hans. (1994). *Dictionary of Symbolism*. New York: Penguin Group.
- Chandler, Daniel. (2007). *Semiotics the Basics*. New York: Routledge.
- Cirlot, J.E. (1971). *A Dictionary of Symbols*. London: Routledge.
- Cuddon, J. (1992). *Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory*. London: Penguin Books.

- Deledalle, Gerard. (2000). *Charles S. Pierce's Philosophy of Signs*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press
- Fatubun, Reimundus Raymond. (2021). [Biblical Allusions in Papuan Mythical Folktales and Their Effects on Material Culture Development for the Papuans](#). (knepublishing.com) (Online) retrieved on October 7, 2021.
- Fatubun, Reimundus Raymond. (2017). An Archetypal Reading the *Manarmakeri* Myth From Biak, Papua: Its Development Implications and Political Significance". [Australian Journal Of Basic And Applied Sciences \(journal-index.org\)](#) (Online) retrieved on 7 October 2021.
- Fatubun, Reimundus Raymond. (2021). *Archetypes in Biak Folktales: Characters, Symbols, and Concepts*([Linguistics and Culture Review \(lingcure.org\)](#)) (Online) retrieved on October 10, 2021.
- Finnegan, R. (2012). *Oral Literature in Africa*. Cambridge: Open Book Publisher.
- Hanita, Margaretha. (2019). *Cita-Cita Koreri: Gerakan Politik Orang Papua*. Jakarta: Universitas Indonesia Publishing.
- Herrero, Baudilio and Cardaño, Mario. (2015). *Ethnobotany in the folksongs of Castilla y León (SPAIN)*. *Botanical Sciences*, 93(2), 1-12
- listiani, Wanda; Rustiyanti, Sri; Sari, FaniDila; and Peradantha, IBG Surya. (2020). Desain Model Purwarupa Augmented Reality Patung Karwar 4.0 Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Seni Tradisi Biak Papua. In *Jurnal Budaya Nusantara*, 3(2), 82-86 (Online) accessed November 12, 2021.
- Inyang, Ofonime. (2018). Fostering Environmental Communication and Human Development through African Indigenous Knowledge: the Example of Selected Ibibio Folksongs. *International Review of Humanities Studies*, 2(1), 59-74
- Kotsonis, Amy. (2014). *Appalachian Folksongs in the Choral Setting: Regional history, traditional performance practice, and guidelines for arranging and performance*. Dissertation.
- Kuusi, M. (1977). *Finish Folk Poetry Epic*, Helsinki: Finnish Literature Society
- Maliangkay, Roald. (2002). The Revival of Folksongs in South Korea: The Case of "Tondollari". *Asian Folklore Studies*, 61(2).
- Mansoben, J.R. (2003). *"Sistem Politik Etnis Byak; Kajian tentang Pemerintahan Tradisional" dalam Jurnal antropologi Papua*, Volume 1 Nomor 3 Agustus 2003. Jayapura: Balai Bahasa Papua
- Nurhadi, (2012). *Peran Sastra Dalam Pendidikan Moral dan Karakter*. Klaten: HISKI.
- Priede, Jānis. (2018). The religious dimension of "forever": From Latvian folksongs to christian texts. *Letonica*, (38)
- Rumansara, Enos H. (2003). *Transforansi Upacara Adat: Wor Dalam Lingkaran Hidup Orang Biak*. Jayapura: Humanora
- Rumbekwan, Alberth. (2019). *Peristiwa-Peristiwa Perang Suku/Tradisional di Pesisir Utara Papua*. Jayapura: IPS, Universitas Cenderawasih
- Sasaki, Christen. (2015). Voices from the Canefields: Folksongs from Japanese Immigrant Workers in Hawai'i by Franklin Odo. *Hawaiian Journal of History*, 49(1), 216-217.
- Simon, Artur; Yampolsky, Philip. (1998). Music of Biak, Irian Jaya: Wor, Church Songs, Yospan. *Yearbook for Traditional Music*, 30
- Sing, Huiem Behari. (1985). *A Study of Manipuri Meitei Folklore*. (Unpublished Ph.D. Tesis). Jalukbari, India: Gauhati University
- Sumiarni, MG Endang; Sundari, E.; Retnowati, Anny; Hartono, Y. (2010). *Hukum Adat Biak*. Jayapura: Biro Hukum Sekretariat Daerah Propinsi Papua.
- Tresidder, Jack. (2011). *1001 Symbols*. London: Walkins Publishing
- Vansina, J. (1985). *Oral Tradition as History*. London: The University of Wisconsin Press.
- Wilkinson, Mary S. (2019) *Five Reasons Why Folk Songs Are So Important*. from (www.teepsnow.com) (Online), Retrieved 07 July 2021.

Author Information

Reimundus Raymond Fatubun

Head of the English Education Graduate Program,
Department of Languages and Arts
Cenderawasih University, Jayapura 99351, Papua,
Indonesia

Markus Ricky Rumansara

Senior MA Student, English Education Graduate
Program, Department of Languages and Arts,
Cenderawasih University, Jayapura 99351, Papua,
Indonesia
